

Supplementary information to the manuscript:

Investigation of Fuel Cell Behavior with Different Catalyst Loadings at Varying Humidities and Temperatures

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Electrochemical active surface area (ECSA) can be calculated from H_{UPD} total charge using the following formula:

$$ECSA = \frac{Q_{HUPD}}{A \times L \times q_{ref}} \quad (S1),$$

Where Q_{HUPD} is total HUPD charge measured by integration of hydrogen desorption region, [mC]; A – geometrical area of the catalyst layer, [cm²]; L – Pt loading, [mg cm⁻²]; q_{ref} is reference charge of flat 1 cm² of Pt, 0.21[mC cm⁻²].

Equilibrium water content, λ, in ionomer can be calculated from the following formula:

$$\lambda = 0.043 + 17.81a_w - 39.85a_w^2 + 36.0a_w^3 \quad (S2),$$

Where a_w is a water activity that is assumed to be equal to RH/100.

Temperature dependence of coverage can be written as follows[1]:

$$\frac{\theta}{1-\theta} = a_{H^+} \exp\left(\frac{-EN_{HEF}}{RT}\right) \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta G_{ads} + g\theta}{RT}\right) \quad (S3)$$

Figure S1. Temperature dependence of hydrogen equilibrium coverage on platinum surface. Relative humidity is 100%.

Unlike [2] we observe closer correspondence to the theoretical trend.

Table S1. Slopes of linear fits to data in Figure 1 a (for H_{UPD}) and b (for C_{DL}).

Parameter/RH	100%RH	75%RH	50%RH	25%RH
H_{UPD} slope ($mCmg_{Pt}^{-1}$)	84.7	68.1	59.1	45.6
C_{DL} slope ($mFmg_{Pt}^{-1}$)	103.5	91.6	84.3	98.9

Measurements of PEM fuel cells with different cathode catalyst layer loading and ionomer content were performed in the range of operating conditions in order to find optimal catalyst layer composition and operating point.

Figure S2. Polarization and power density curves of PEM fuel cells with cathode catalyst layer loadings of 0.2 (a), 0.4 (b), 0.8 (c), and 1.0 mg_{Pt} cm⁻² (d). All measurements were performed at 70°C at relative humidities of 100, 75, 50, 25, and 0%. Data were used for Figure 4 of the main manuscript.

Figure S3. Polarization and power density curves of PEM fuel cells at different temperatures and humidities. Cathode catalyst layer loading of $0.4 \text{ mg}_{\text{Pt}} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, ionomer-to-carbon ratio of 0.6. Measurements were performed at temperatures of $70 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (a), $60 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (b), $50 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (c), $40 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ (d) and humidities shown in the graphs. Data were used for Figure 5 of the main manuscript.

Figure S4. Polarization and power density curves of PEM fuel cells at different temperatures and humidities. Cathode catalyst layer loading of $0.4\text{mg}_{\text{Pt}}\text{cm}^{-2}$, ionomer-to-carbon ratio of 0.8. Measurements were performed at temperatures of 70 °C (a), 60 °C (b), 50 °C (c), 40 °C (d) and humidities shown in the graphs. Data were used for Figure 5 of the main manuscript

Figure S5. Peak performance (a) and current density at 0.6 V (b) for samples with different catalyst loadings measured at different relative humidities. Cell temperature was set at 70 °C ; I/C ratio at 0.6. Presented graphs are supplement of Figure 4 with adding of the confidence

intervals.

Figure S6. Peak performance of samples with catalyst loading of 0.4 mgPtcm⁻² and I/C ratios of 0.6 (a) and 0.8 (b), measured at different relative humidities and temperatures. Presented graphs are supplement of Figure 5 with adding of the confidence interval.

Figure S7. SEM images of cathode catalyst layer (CCL) and MEA crosssections for sample with catalyst loading of 0.4 mgPt/cm² and I/C ratio of 0.6.

I/C ratio of 0.6 before and after operation at low humidity level (60 hours total at 0% RH).

Figure S8. SEM images of cathode catalyst layer (CCL) and MEA crosssections for sample with I/C ratio of 0.8 before and after operation at low humidity level (60 hours total at 0% RH).

Figure S9. EIS measurements of MEAs with Pt loading in cathode catalyst layer of 0.4 mg cm^{-2}

and I/C ratio of 0.6 (left) and 0.8 (right). Measurements were performed at 70 °C with H₂/N₂ feed. Systems demonstrate stability in HFR suggesting low/no degradation in membrane, however linear part of impedance in high frequency region differs in length, suggesting changes in ion transport in the catalyst layer. Both catalyst layers showed increase of ion transport resistance after dry operation. Catalyst layer with lower ionomer content shows, however slightly bigger increase in ion transport resistance.